

PYU STAMPED AND ROULETTED CERAMICS FROM THE YAHANDA MOUND SRI KSETRA MYANMAR

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Kyaw Myo Win, Tin May Oo, Myint Aung, Nyo Nyo Yin Mauk, Yin
Nyein Aye, Naw Pauk Wah**

**A JOINT PROJECT OF THE MCDONALD INSTITUTE FOR ARCHAEOLOGICAL RESEARCH, UNIVERSITY
OF CAMBRIDGE & THE FIELD SCHOOL OF ARCHAEOLOGY, DEPARTMENT OF ARCHAEOLOGY &
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**SRI KSETRA TODAY IN
THE DRY SEASON – RED
AREAS CONTAIN HIGH
LEVELS OF ORGANIC
MATTER; BLACK SPOTS
ARE SURFACE WATER.
THE YAHANDA MOUND IS
JUST OUTSIDE THE
SOUTH-WEST CITY WALLS**

**YAHANDA MOUND SRI KSETRA:
ORIGINS OF SETTLEMENT
BELONG TO THE C. 1STC. BCE, NO
BUDDHISM OR HINDUISM BUT
EVIDENCE OF TECHNICAL
CONTACTS WITH INDIA IN
WATER CONTROL, IRON AND
CERAMICS; PYU STAMPED AND
ROULETTED CERAMICS
OCCURRED MAINLY IN THE 4TH –
6TH CENTURY TOGETHER WITH
EVIDENCE OF EARLY CONTACTS
WITH BUDDHISM AND
HINDUISM**

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Sri Ksetra, the Yahanda Mound with excavated areas and urban context [Gabriel Amable and Janice Stargardt].

FIGURE SHOWING
DISTRIBUTION OF PITS IN
RELATION TO SLOPE OF THE
YAHANDA MOUND

Elevation (m)

62 - 62.2	62.9 - 63	63.7 - 63.8
62.3 - 62.4	63.1 - 63.2	63.9 - 64
62.5 - 62.6	63.3 - 63.4	64.1 - 64.2
62.7 - 62.8	63.5 - 63.6	64.3 - 64.8

0 2.5 5 10 15 Meters

- Contours at 0.1m intervals
- Approx. location of pits
- Pit tent enclosures

Sri Ksetra Yahanda Mound, AMS dates by Beta Analytics November 2016

SUBMITTERNo.	SERVICES	MATERIAL/ PRETREATMENT	CONVENTIONAL AGE	2SIGMA CALIBRATION	2SIGMA CALIBRATION PDF	STABLE ISOTOPES & CN
H59/8/5-6 /100-10	AMS-Standard delivery	(Charred Material): Acid/alkali/acid	1610 +/- 30 BP	Cal AD 390 to 540 (Cal BP 1560 to 1410)		δ13C (‰) -27.3
H59/8/6-7/140	AMS-Micro-sample Analysis; Standard delivery	(Charred Material): Acid/alkali/acid	1680 +/- 30 BP	Cal AD 260 to 280 (Cal BP 1690 to 1670) and Cal AD 325 to 420 (Cal BP 1625 to 1530)		δ13C (‰) -25.7
H59/9/8/175	CANCELED					
H59/3/68	AMS-Standard delivery	(Charred Material): Acid/alkali/acid	1290 +/- 30 BP	Cal AD 660 to 770 (Cal BP 1290 to 1180)		δ13C (‰) -27.3

**YAHANDA MOUND, SRI
KSETRA, TP8
CULTURAL SEQUENCE
12 CREMATED BURIALS
WITHOUT OFFERINGS
IN LAYERS 9 – 7;
ANCIENT WOODEN
FLOOR AND POST HOLE
IN LAYER 6;
HABITATION DEBRIS IN
LAYERS
5 - 3**

**Yahanda Mound Sri
Ksetra, TP8, burial urn
from Pre-Buddhist and
Hindu layer but
showing Indic
techniques in ceramic
forming**

**STAMPED AND ROULETTED SHERD WITH SRIVATSA MOTIF
FROM YAHANDA MOUND SRI KSETRA, FOUND JUST ABOVE
THE FLOOR IN TP8, MID- OR LATE-4TH CENT.**

**YAHANDA
MOUND, SRI
KSETRA, TP8
CONTEXT 3-4
IN HARDENED
WORK
SURFACE.
FRAGMENT OF
CLAY SEALING
WITH HEAD OF
BUDDHA IN
NICHE WITH
FOLIAGE
ABOVE**

**YAHANDA GU SRI
KSETRA, STAMPED
AND ROULETTED
SHERDS WITH 2
FORMS OF KAILASA
POT, SYMBOL OF
PLENTY IN BOTH
BUDDHISM AND
HINDUISM; NOTE
PRESENCE OF VISNU
CONCH SHELL AND
LOCAL MOTIF OF
DANCING MAN**

STAMPED SHERD WITH BORDERS OF RAISED DOTS FROM YAHANDA MOUND, SRI KSETRA TP8, CONTEXT 6 RIGHT ON ANCIENT FLOOR, 4TH CENT. CE, HEROIC OR DIVINE NUDE MALE AND FEMALE FIGURES DEPICTED SEPARATELY, WEARING HEAD DRESSES, HEAVY EARRINGS, MALE WEARING HEAVY ANKLETS, FEMALE HEAVY BANGLE, BOTH CARRYING RITUAL? OBJECTS

- **STAMPED SHERD WITH BORDERS OF RAISED DOTS FROM YAHANDA MOUND, SRI KSETRA TP8, CONTEXT 4, C. 6TH CENT., DEPICTING SPIRIT-ANCESTOR(?) COUPLE WEARING HIGH PLUMED HEAD DRESSES, HEAVY EARRINGS AND ANKLETS AND THIN SKIRTS**

**YAHANDA MOUND SRI
KSETRA, TP10, STAMPED
AND ROULETTED SHERD
SHOWING HEROIC NUDE
MALE FIGURE HOLDING
LONG BOW IN HIS PROPER
RIGHT HAND AND A
STANDARD IN HIS LEFT.
STAMP BELOW SUGGESTS
THE FIGURE WORE A HEAD
DRESS**

**SRI KSETRA
SURFACE FIND,
STAMPED SHERD
SHOWING MAN
WITH WHIP RACING
ON A HUMP-
BACKED BULL,
TRACES OF
ROULETTING
AROUND STAMP**

COURTESY KO KYA PAN, PYAY

CONCLUSIONS:

1. **YAHANDA MOUND, SRI KSETRA** is the only known Pyu habitation site; it permits the study of culture, and cultural change over a nearly a millennium on a popular level
2. First occupation **Pre-Buddhist Pyu culture**: grouped cremation burials without offerings, in urns, in burial terraces of compacted earth; **latest burial c. 260+/-30 CE; earliest 3 geological layers lower**
3. Dense habitation debris directly above the floors dates to **c. 340+/-30 CE** and contains possibly earliest stratified evidence in Southeast Asia of Buddhism and Hinduism on a popular level: i.e. **sherds stamped with Buddhist and Hindu motifs and royal or divine figures**. But stamped and rouletted sherds also show Indian ceramic techniques **provided the pictorial language to depict their own culture in their own ways.**

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